

Unusual Schmidt reaction of some 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones[†]

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Schmidt reaction of 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones (**1**) affords 2-(α -aminobenzylidene)indane-1,3-diones (**2**) and/or indeno[1,2-*b*]quinolin-11-ones (**3**) in fairly good yields depending upon the nature of the substituent(s) in the benzylidene phenyl ring.

Schmidt reaction of ketones has since long been used for the synthesis of N-substituted amides and lactams¹⁻⁶. In case of unsymmetrical cyclic ketones, depending upon the steric and electronic factors, however, ring enlargement can occur on either side of the ketonic moiety giving a mixture of isomeric lactams⁷⁻¹⁰. Beside these normal ring enlargement products, certain unusual products such as tetrazoles and nitriles have also been reported¹¹⁻¹⁴.

In this paper, we wish to report an unusual Schmidt reaction of some 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones (**1**). Treatment of **1** with hydrazoic acid (generated *in situ* by the action of conc. H₂SO₄ on NaN₃) in anhydrous benzene gave, on usual work-up and chromatography, 2-(α -amino-benzylidene)indane-1,3-diones (**2**) and/or indeno[1,2-*b*]-quinolin-11 ones (**3**) in fairly good yields depending upon the nature of the substituent in the benzylidene phenyl ring according to Scheme 1.

The structures of the products have been fully characterized through their IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectra (vide Experimental). The IR spectra of the α -amination products (**2**) displayed two bands of medium intensity in the region 3420–3450 cm⁻¹ and 3282–3350 cm⁻¹ due respectively to asymmetric and symmetric stretch of the NH₂ group besides two strong bands at 1720 cm⁻¹ and 1680 cm⁻¹ due respectively to asymmetric and symmetric splitting of >C=O stretch by coupling between two in-plane carbonyl groups of indane-1,3-dione moiety¹⁵. The most diagnostic feature of the ¹H NMR spectra of **2** was the appearance of two one-proton doublets of doublets in the region δ 8.07–8.12 and 8.10–8.18 (*J* 7.41–7.5 Hz and 1.2–1.4 Hz) for H-7 and H-4 respectively which are deshielded to different extents because of their location in slightly different environments whereas 7-H is deshielded by H-bonded carbonyl group at C-1 while 4-H is deshielded by free carbonyl group at

Scheme 1

1	2 (% yield)	3 (% yield)
a R = R ₁ = R ₂ = H	60.3	–
b R = NO ₂ , R ₁ = R ₂ = H	55.4	–
c R = CH ₃ , R ₁ = R ₂ = H	46.2	10.5
d R = Cl, R ₁ = R ₂ = H	43.4	8.5
e R = OCH ₃ , R ₁ = R ₂ = H	–	56.5
f R = R ₁ = OCH ₃ , R ₂ = H	–	58.3
g R = R ₁ = R ₂ = OCH ₃	–	52.4

1-C₃. The IR spectra of **3** exhibited two strong peaks in the region 1712–1720 cm⁻¹ and 1620–1628 cm⁻¹ due to C=O stretch in a five-membered ring ketone and >C=N stretch respectively.

Further confirmation of the cyclization products (**3**) came from their ¹H NMR spectra, which displayed a characteristic one-proton singlet in the region δ 8.22–8.35 due to H-10. The deshielding of this proton is partly due to –I-effect of the N atom and partly due to anisotropic effect of the contiguous >C=O group at 11-C. The structures of the azapolycyclics (**3**) were further corroborated by the chemical shift of H-6 which varied considerably in a predictable manner depending upon the nature of the substituent at 7-C. In case of **3d** (R = Cl, R₁ = R₂ = H), due

[†]Dedicated to our teacher Professor S. M. Mukherji.

the electron-withdrawing nature of Cl, H-6 was substantially deshielded and appeared as a doublet at δ 8.13 (J 1.2 Hz). However, in case of **3c** ($R = \text{CH}_3$, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$) and **3e** ($R = \text{OCH}_3$, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$), due to electron-donating effect of the CH_3 and OCH_3 groups, H-6 got shielded and appeared as doublets in the region δ 7.90–7.91 and 7.52–7.53 respectively. In case of **3f** ($R = R_1 = \text{OCH}_3$, $R_2 = \text{H}$) due to the presence of two OCH_3 groups at 8-C and 7-C, H-6 got further shielded and appeared as a singlet at δ 7.26.

The relative yields of the products (**2** and **3**) suggest that 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones (**1a**) and the presence of *m*-directing group such as NO_2 group at *p*-position of benzylidene phenyl group favour the formation of α -amination products, **2a** and **2b**, while presence of weakly *o,p*-directing groups such as CH_3 , Cl etc. favour the formation of both amination and cyclization products (**2** and **3** respectively) but the presence of one or more strongly electron-donating groups at *m*- and *p*-positions favour the formation of only the cyclization products, i.e., **3e-g**.

Mechanistically, the formation of **2** can be envisaged to have occurred through Michael type nucleophilic attack by the hydrazoic acid at the β -carbon of the α,β -unsaturated moiety followed by loss of N_2 with concomitant 1,2-hydride shift to the electron deficient N-atom (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

In contrast, formation of **3** may involve an initial nucleophilic attack by the N-atom of the hydrazoic acid on the carbonyl group to form an intermediate (**4**), which subsequently loses a molecule of H_2O to afford the intermediate **5**. The intermediate **5** may either (i) undergo a thermal 6π -electrocyclic reaction to afford another intermediate **6** which subsequently undergoes aromatization with the loss of a proton and a molecule of N_2 to yield **3** or (ii) **5** may undergo a nucleophilic attack by the benzene ring with the removal of N_2 molecule to give a cabocation (**7**) which subsequently loses a proton to give **3** (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Experimental

Melting points were determined using open capillaries in H_2SO_4 bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr pellet, or nujol mull) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Paragon 1000 PL FT-IR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded with solutions in CDCl_3 on a 90 MHz Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer or a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer. The chemical shifts are reported on δ scale using TMS as the internal standard. Low resolution MS were recorded at 70 eV using VG-70S instrument. Silica gel (100–200 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

General procedure for the Schmidt reaction of 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones (1):

To a well-stirred suspension of 2-benzylideneindane-1,3-diones (0.004 mol) in a mixture of benzene (10 ml) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml) was added sodium azide (0.05 mol) in small proportions. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 3 h at 50–60°, the completion of reaction being monitored by TLC. Thereafter the reaction mixture was cooled, poured over crushed ice and extracted with chloroform (100 ml); the organic extract was washed first with water (100 ml) and then with a solution of brine (50 ml), and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . Finally the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution of the column with a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) gave bright red crystals of 2-(α -amino-benzylidene)indane-

1,3-diones (2). Further elution of the column with a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate (80 : 20) gave yellow crystals of the corresponding indenol[1,2-*b*]-quinolin-11-ones (3).

2-(α -Aminobenzylidene)indane-1,3-dione (2a) :

Bright red crystals, m.p. 176° (benzene-pet ether), yield 60.3%; m/z 249 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 248 (74.9), 232 (4.3), 221 (18.1), 220 (38.2), 204 (14.7), 193 (5.8), 165 (26.3), 144 (7.0), 104 (10.0), 89 (10.0), 76 (19.1); ν_{\max} 3420, 3282 (m, asym and sym N-H str), 1720, 1680 (s, asym and sym C=O str of indane-1,3-dione) cm^{-1} ; δ 5.2 (2H, br s, NH_2 , exchangeable with D_2O), 7.34–7.41 (3H, m, H-3', H-4', H-5'), 7.47–7.52 (2H, m, H-2', H-6'), 7.63–7.68 (1H, dt, H-5, J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 7.72–7.77 (1H, dt, H-6 J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 8.08–8.11 (1H, dd, H-7, J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 8.14–8.17 (1H, dd, H-4, J 7.4 and 1.3 Hz).

2-(α -Amino-4'-nitrobenzylidene)indane-1,3-dione (2b) :

Bright red crystals, m.p. 245–246° (acetone-pet ether), yield 55.4%; m/z 294 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 293 (23.3), 248 (36.1), 247 (45.3), 221 (5.5), 220 (14.8), 219 (12.7), 190 (10.6), 165 (20.6), 104 (14.8); ν_{\max} 3450, 3320 (m, asym and sym N-H str), 1720, 1680 (s, asym and sym C=O str of indane-1,3-dione), 1580, 1330 (s, asym and sym NO_2 str) cm^{-1} ; δ 5.2 (2H, br s, NH_2 , exchangeable with D_2O), 7.57–7.61 (2H, d, H-2', H-6', J 8.5 Hz), 7.67–7.73 (2H, m, H-5, H-6), 8.12–8.18 (2H, m, H-4, H-7), 8.34–8.36 (2H, d, H-3', H-5', J 8.5 Hz).

2-(α -Amino-4'-methylbenzylidene)indane-1,3-dione (2c) :

Bright red crystals, m.p. 196–197° (chloroform-pet ether), yield 46.2%; m/z 263 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 262 (46.9), 248 (91.3), 234 (26.5), 220 (15.4), 218 (11.8), 178 (10.0), 165 (15.5), 104 (11.9), 77 (17.8), 76 (24.4); ν_{\max} 3450, 3320 (m, asym and sym N-H str), 1720, 1680 (s, asym and sym, C=O str of indane-1,3-dione) cm^{-1} ; δ 2.4 (3H, s, 4'- CH_3), 5.2 (2H, br s, NH_2 , exchangeable with D_2O), 7.23–7.26 (2H, d, H-3', H-5', J 8.1 Hz), 7.28–7.31 (2H, d, H-2', H-6', J 8.1 Hz), 7.62–7.67 (1H, dt, H-5, J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 7.71–7.76 (1H, dt, H-6, J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 8.07–8.10 (1H, dd, H-4 J 7.4 and 1.4 Hz), 8.13–8.16 (1H, dd, H-7, J 7.4 and 1.4 Hz).

2-(α -Amino-4'-chlorobenzylidene)indane-1,3-dione (2d) :

Bright red crystals, m.p. 220–221° (acetone-pet ether), yield 43.4%; m/z 285 ($M^{+\bullet}+2$, 100)/283 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 87.5), 284 (29.5)/282 (30.1), 257 (1.7)/255 (8.1), 256 (12.8)/254 (17.8), 249 (23.2), 248 (100.0), 238 (7.5), 220 (18.0), 165 (26.3), 104 (19.4), 76 (34.7); ν_{\max} 3450, 3350 (m,

asym and sym N-H str), 1720, 1680 (s, asym and sym C=O str of indane-1,3-dione) cm^{-1} ; δ 5.2 (2H, br s, NH_2 , exchangeable with D_2O), 7.29–7.32 (2H, d, H-3', H-5', J 8.3 Hz), 7.45–7.48 (2H, d, H-2', H-6', J 8.3 Hz), 7.63–7.68 (1H, dt, H-5, J 7.4 and 1.2 Hz), 7.72–7.77 (1H, dt, H-6, J 7.4 and 1.2 Hz), 8.08–8.11 (1H, dd, H-7 J 7.5 and 1.2 Hz), 8.13–8.15 (1H, dd, H-4, J 7.6 and 1.2 Hz).

7-Methylindenol[1,2-*b*]quinolin-11-one (3c) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 160–161° (ethanol), yield 10.5%; m/z 244 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 217 (8.2), 216 (14.9) 189 (7.3); ν_{\max} 1720 (s, C=O str), 1620 (s, C=N str) cm^{-1} ; δ 2.6 (3H, s, 7- CH_3), 7.34–7.37 (1H, dd, H-8, J 8.1 and 1.4 Hz), 7.48–7.53 (1H, dt, H-2, J 8.1 and 1.1 Hz), 7.64–7.70 (1H, dt, H-3, J 8.1 and 1.1 Hz), 7.74–7.77 (1H, d, H-9, J 8.2 Hz), 7.80–7.83 (1H, d, H-1 J 8.2 Hz), 7.90–7.91 (1H, d, H-6, J 1.4 Hz), 8.06–8.09 (1H, dd, H-4, J 8.0 and 1.2 Hz), 8.32 (1H, s, H-10).

7-Chloroindenol[1,2-*b*]quinolin-11-one (3d) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 180–181° (ethanol), yield 8.5%; m/z 267 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100)/265 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100); ν_{\max} 1720 (s, C=O str), 1620 (s, C=N str) cm^{-1} ; δ 7.49–7.55 (1H, dd, H-8, J 8.6 and 1.6 Hz), 7.55–7.57 (1H, d, H-9, J 8.2 Hz), 7.69–7.74 (1H, dt, H-2, J 8.0 and 1.1 Hz), 7.80–7.86 (2H, m, H-1, H-3), 8.08–8.11 (1H, dd, H-4, J 8.0 and 1.2 Hz), 8.13 (1H, d, H-6 J 1.2 Hz), 8.35 (1H, s, H-10).

7-Methoxyindenol[1,2-*b*]quinolin-11-one (3e) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 179–180° (ethanol), yield 56.5%; m/z 261 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 246 (1.0), 233 (2.2), 232 (11.6), 231 (12.6), 218 (43.6), 190 (21.4), 163 (6.3); ν_{\max} 1720 (s, C=O str), 1620 (s, C=N str) cm^{-1} ; δ 4.0 (3H, s, 7- OCH_3), 7.15–7.19 (1H, dd, H-8, J 8.8 and 1.2 Hz), 7.48–7.50 (1H, dt, H-2, J 7.5 and 1.1 Hz), 7.52–7.53 (1H, d, H-6, J 1.2 Hz), 7.63–7.69 (1H, dt, H-3, J 7.0 and 1.1 Hz), 7.74–7.76 (1H, d, H-9 J 8.8 Hz), 7.79–7.82 (1H, dd, H-1, J 7.9 and 1.1 Hz), 8.04–8.07 (1H, dd, H-4 J 8.1 and 1.1 Hz), 8.30 (1H, s, H-10).

7,8-Dimethoxyindenol[1,2-*b*]quinolin-11-one (3f) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 170–171° (benzene-pet ether), yield 58.3%; m/z 291 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 100), 276 (19.0), 249 (8.8), 248 (51.6), 220 (10.4), 219 (5.3), 218 (15.4), 205 (39.2), 190 (7.6), 178 (5.5), 177 (24.2), 151 (18.5), 150 (20.6); ν_{\max} 1718 (s, C=O str), 1628 (s, C=N str) cm^{-1} ; δ 4.04 (3H, s, 8- OCH_3), 4.09 (3H, s, 7- OCH_3), 7.11 (1H, s, H-9), 7.26 (1H, s, H-6), 7.44–7.48 (1H, dt, H-2, J 8.0 and 1.2 Hz), 7.61–7.66 (1H, dt, H-3, J 7.3 and 1.2 Hz), 7.77–7.79 (1H, d, H-1, J 8.7 Hz), 7.98–8.01 (1H, d, H-4, J 8.4 Hz), 8.22 (1H, s, H-10).

6,7,8-Trimethoxyindeno[1,2-b]quinolin-11-one (3g) :

Yellow crystals, m.p. 171–172° (benzene-pet ether), yield 52.4%; m/z 321 ($M^{+\bullet}$, 37.2), 320 (20.6), 307 (26.4), 306 (100), 292 (22.1), 290 (19.7), 277 (9.2), 275 (22.2), 262 (12.8), 260 (18.9), 164 (30.6); ν_{\max} 1712 (s, C=O str), 1623 (s, C=N str) cm^{-1} ; δ 4.00 (3H, s, 8-OCH₃), 4.09 (3H, s, 7-OCH₃), 4.23 (3H, s, 6-OCH₃), 6.95 (1H, s, H-9), 7.44–7.49 (1H, dt, H-2 J 8.0 and 1.2 Hz), 7.62–7.67 (1H, dt, H-3, J 7.3 and 1.3 Hz), 7.77–7.80 (1H, dd, H-1, J 8.7 Hz), 8.08–8.11 (1H, dd, H-4 J 8.4 Hz), 8.22 (1H, s, H-10).

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